

**FOK FAZOSINING QIRQILGAN IKKI ZARRACHALI QISM
FAZOSIDA BERILGAN DISKRET PARAMETRLI IKKINCHI TARTIBLI
OPERATORLI MATRITSANI CHIZIQLILIKKA TEKSHIRISH.**

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Annotatsiya. Garchi amaliyotda chiziqli bo'lmagan operatorlar ko'proq uchrasada, fizika va matematikada muhim jarayonlarni tavsiflash uchun chiziqli operatorlarga ko'proq murojaat etiladi. Chunki chiziqli operatorlar bir qator muhim xususiyatlarga egadirki, umumiy holda istalgan operator bunday xossalarga ega deb ayta olmaymiz. Misol uchun, chiziqli operatorlar uchun nuqtada uzluksizlik, butun fazoda uzluksizlik va chegaralanganlik tushunchalari ekvivalentdir. Shuning uchun mazkur mavzu dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Gilbert fazosi, Fok fazosi, skalyar ko'paytma, kompleks fazo, qo'shma operatorlar, o'z – o'ziga qo'shma operator.

Annotation. Although nonlinear operators are more common in practice, linear operators are more often referenced to describe important processes in physics and mathematics. Because linear operators have a number of important properties that, in general, we cannot say that any operator has such properties. For example, for linear operators, the concepts of continuity at a point, continuity over an entire space, and delimitation are equivalent. Therefore, this topic is relevant.

Keywords: Gilbert space, Fok space, scalar product, complex space, additive operators, self – adjoint operator.

$H_0 := \mathbb{C}$ - bir o‘lchamli kompleks fazo, $H_1 := L_2(\mathbb{T}^d) - \mathbb{T}^d$ da aniqlangan kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi, (umuman olganda, kompleks qiymatli) funksiyalar Gilbert fazosi bo‘lsin. $H^{(2)}$ orqali H_0 va H_1 fazolarning to‘g‘ri yig‘indisini belgilaymiz, ya‘ni $H^{(2)} := H_0 \oplus H_1$ [1].

Odatda, $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosiga Fok fazosining qirqilgan ikki zarrachali qism fazosi deyiladi. $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosining ixtiyoriy f elementi $f = (f_0, f_1)$ kabi tasvirlanadi, bunda $f_0 \in H_0, f_1 \in H_1$ [1].

$f = (f_0, f_1) \in H^{(2)}$ elementning normasi

$$\|f\| = \sqrt{\|f_0\|_0^2 + \|f_1\|_1^2}$$

formula yordamida topiladi:

$$\|f_0\|_0 = |f_0|, \quad \|f_1\|_1 = \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{T}^d} \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |f_1(t)|^2 dt.}$$

Ikkita $f = (f_0, f_1), g = (g_0, g_1) \in H^{(2)}$ elementlarning skalyar ko‘paytmasi

$$(f, g) = (f_0, g_0)_0 + (f_1, g_1)_1$$

kabi topiladi:

$$(f_0, g_0)_0 = f_0 \cdot \overline{g_0}, \quad (f_1, g_1)_1 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} f_1(t) \overline{g_1(t)} dt.$$

$H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosida quyidagi ikkinchi tartibli

$$A_2^{(s)} := \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A}_{00}^{(s)} & \hat{A}_{01} \\ \hat{A}_{01}^* & \hat{A}_{11}^{(s)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

operatorli matritsani qaraymiz, bu yerda $A_{ij}: H_i \rightarrow H_i, i = 0, 1, A_{01}: H_1 \rightarrow H_0$

operatorlar quyidagicha aniqlangan: $\hat{A}_{00}^{(s)} f_0 = s \varepsilon f_0, f_0 \in H_0;$

$\hat{A}_{01} f_1 = \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t) f_1(t) dt, f_1 \in H_1; (\hat{A}_{11}^{(s)} f_1)(x) = (-s \varepsilon + u(x)) f_1(x), f_1 \in H_1.$

Bunda, $s = \pm, \varepsilon$ - haqiqiy son, $v(\cdot)$ va $u(\cdot)$ lar haqiqiy qiymatli uzluksiz funksiyalar, $\alpha > 0$ - esa “ta’sirlashuv parametri”, \hat{A}_{01}^* operator mos ravishda \hat{A}_{01} operatorga qo‘shma operatorlar bo‘lib, ular quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$(\hat{A}_{01} f_1, f_0) = (f_1, f_0 \hat{A}_{01}^*)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\hat{A}_{01}f_1, f_0) &= \left(\alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt, f_0 \right) = \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt, \bar{f}_0 = \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} \overline{\alpha v(t)f_0} f_1(t)dt = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} f_1(t)\overline{\alpha v(t)f_0}dt \\ \hat{A}_{01}^* &= \alpha v(t)f_0 \quad (\hat{A}_{01}^*f_0)(x) = \alpha v(x)f_0, \quad f_0 \in H_0. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma. $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosida (1) formula orqali ta'sir qiluvchi

ikkinchi tartibli $A_2^{(s)}$ operatorli matritsa chiziqli, chegaralangan va o'z – o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'ladi [2].

Ta'rif. Agar ixtiyoriy $a, b \in \mathbb{C}$ kompleks sonlar va ixtiyoriy $f = (f_0, f_1), g = (g_0, g_1) \in H^{(2)}$ elementlar uchun

$$A_2^{(s)}(af + bg) = aA_2^{(s)}f + bA_2^{(s)}g$$

tenglik bajarilsa $A_2^{(s)}$ operatorli matritsa chiziqli operator deyiladi.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Demak bunda } A_2^{(s)}f &:= \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A}_{00}^{(s)} & \hat{A}_{01} \\ \hat{A}_{01}^* & \hat{A}_{11}^{(s)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f_0 \\ f_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A}_{00}^{(s)}f_0 + \hat{A}_{01}f_1 \\ \hat{A}_{01}^*f_0 + \hat{A}_{11}^{(s)}f_1 \end{pmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} s\epsilon f_0 + \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \\ \alpha v(x)f_0 + (-s\epsilon + u(x))f_1(x) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

ekanligini ta'kidlab o'tamiz.

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